

developmentSEED

Use Case Promotion Package

Global Fish Tracking System

FOR
BY ESA and Starion
 Development Seed

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Introduction

This document describes the use case promotion package for the Global Fish Tracking Software (GFTS) DestinE Platform use case. GFTS is a complex system, so we have focused on good public communication and simplified documentation that helps interested parties understand the project goals and the system itself as well.

Promotional material

Website

<https://destination-earth.eu/use-cases/global-fish-tracking-system-gfts/>

Documentation

https://destination-earth.github.io/DestinE_ESA_GFTS/intro.html

Participation in conferences

The following link contains an updated list of communications that our team is creating under the GFTS project.

https://destination-earth.github.io/DestinE_ESA_GFTS/outreach.html

Current list of publications from conferences and other events

Below is a list of publications and conferences (starting from the most recent) that made use of GFTS resources and/or promoted the GFTS project:

- Wiesmann, D., Fouilloux, A., Odaka, T., Ragan-Kelly, B., Woillez, M., Mazouni, Q., Autret, E.: Global Fish Tracking System (GFTS): Harnessing Technological Innovations for Conservation and Sustainable Resource Management, LPS25, Vienna, Austria, 23-27 June 2025.
- Odaka, T., Woillez, M., Fouilloux, A., Ragan-Kelly, B., Autret, E., and Wiesmann, D.: Global Fish Tracking System: Leveraging Destination Earth and Biologging Data for Climate Change Insights,

Conservation, and Sustainable Use, One Ocean Science Congress 2025, Nice, France, 3–6 Jun 2025, OOS2025-1044, [10.5194/oos2025-1044](https://doi.org/10.5194/oos2025-1044), 2025.

- Magin, J., Mazouni, Q., Cap, E., Gonse, M., Woillez, M., Fouilloux, A., Delouis, J.-M., & Odaka, T. (2025). pangeo-fish (2025.03.3). Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.15110143](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110143)
- Odaka, T., Fouilloux, A., Wiesmann, D., Autret, E., Woillez, M., and Ragan-Kelley, B.: The Global Fish Tracking System for Impactful Marine Conservation, 3rd Destination Earth User eXchange, Darmstadt, Germany, 15–16 Oct 2024, EGU24-15500, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15224060](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15224060)
- Fouilloux, Anne, and Benjamin Ragan-Kelley. Simula's Contribution to the Global Fish Tracking System (GFTS) on the Destine Platform, presentation given at the [Norwegian Destination Earth info meeting](#), 13 May 2024, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11187870](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11187870)
- Wiesmann, D., Odaka, T., Fouilloux, A., Autret, E., Woillez, M., and Ragan-Kelley, B.: Harnessing the Pangeo ecosystem for delivering the cloud-based Global Fish Tracking System, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-10741, Poster: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11104925> DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-egu24-10741](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-10741)
- Odaka, T., Fouilloux, A., Wiesmann, D., Autret, E., Woillez, M., and Ragan-Kelley, B.: Advancing Marine Ecosystem Conservation with the Global Fish Tracking System on the Destination Earth Service Platform, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-15500, DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-egu24-15500](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-15500)
- Odaka, Tina Erica, Justus Magne, Marine Gonse, and Mathieu Woillez. Leveraging Pangeo to Geolocate Fish Using Biologging Data: The Pangeo-fish Initiative (version 1.0). Zenodo, 12 March 2024, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10809819](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10809819).
- Woillez, Mathieu, Daniel Wiesmann, Anne Fouilloux, Tina Erica Odaka, Benjamin Ragan-Kelley, Olaf Veerman, Emmanuelle Autret, Ricardo Mestre, and Daniel da Silva. 'Global Fish Tracking System - DESP Use Case', presentation given at [Roadshow Webinar: DestinE in action – meet the first DESP use cases](#), 13 December 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10372387](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10372387)
- Woillez, M., Wiesmann, D., Fouilloux, A., Odaka, T. E., Ragan-Kelley, B., Veerman, O., Autret, E., Mestre, R., & da Silva, D. (2023, December 13). Global Fish Tracking System - DESP Use Case. 2nd DestinE User eXchange Poster, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10372387](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10372387)
- Wiesmann, Daniel, Tina Erica Odaka, Anne Fouilloux, Mathieu Woillez, Emmanuelle Autret, Benjamin Ragan-Kelley, Ricardo Mestre, Daniel da Silva, and Olaf Veerman. 'Global Fish Tracking System Kickoff'. 7 November 2023. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10213946](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10213946).

GFTS Massive Open Online Course

As part of this project we have also developed the material for a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) module that will be published as part of the overarching DesintE use case MOOC.